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UNDERSTANDING PHYSICS-GUIDED MACHINE LEARNING: APPLICATIONS, TRENDS, AND CHALLENGES FOR AEROSPACE

The article provides a systematic review of the PGML concept as a new approach to modeling complex engineering problems in aerospace engineering. Particular attention is focused on how the integration of physical laws with machine learning algorithms transforms traditional approaches to analysis, design, and operation of structures. The principles underlying PGML are examined: modification of the loss function to account for residuals of physical equations, constructive embedding of symmetries into the model structure, and the development of a computational space based on physical invariants. The methodology of this work is based on the analysis of four aerospace-related problems: material fatigue prediction, flutter prediction—an aerodynamic phenomenon characterized by unstable self-oscillations of structures—design of thin-walled structures, and structural condition monitoring. Approximately 30 peer-reviewed sources were analyzed, enabling the identification of key directions for implementation in the design and analysis of the aerospace industry. A limitation of the PGML analysis is the limited number of published sources, which may be somewhat superficial. Key PGML implementations—namely PINNs, GAPINN, NSFnet, multi-fidelity, and hybrid models—and their effectiveness in cases of limited data samples are analyzed. Attention is also given to model interpretability issues, including the application of explainable ML, symbolic regression, and Bayesian approaches for solution verification in critical scenarios. The main challenges for widespread PGML adoption are identified: balancing physical and statistical components, scalability limitations in multiphase environments, certification complexity, and instability in solving inverse problems. The study concludes that PGML transcends being a mere application of machine learning and emerges as a new epistemological platform for formulating engineering hypotheses.

Keywords: PGML, PINNs, flutter, fatigue life, multi-fidelity modeling, turbulence closure

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РОЗУМІННЯ ФІЗИЧНО-КЕРОВАНОГО МАШИННОГО НАВЧАННЯ: ЗАСТОСУВАННЯ, ТЕНДЕНЦІЇ ТА ВИКЛИКИ ДЛЯ АЕРОКОСМІЧНОЇ ГАЛУЗІ

У статті здійснено системний огляд концепції PGML як нового підходу до моделювання складних інженерних задач у сфері аерокосмічного машинобудування. Особливу увагу зосереджено на тому, як поєднання фізичних закономірностей із

алгоритмами машинного навчання трансформує традиційні підходи до аналізу, проектування й експлуатації конструкцій. Розглянуто принципи, на яких ґрунтується PGML: модифікація функції втрат із урахуванням залишків фізичних рівнянь, конструктивне вбудовування симетрій у структуру моделі, а також побудова обчислювального простору на основі фізичних інваріантів. Методологія даної роботи ґрунтується на аналізі чотирьох задач які зв'язані з аерокосмічною галуззю: прогнозування втоми матеріалів, прогнозування флатеру – тобто це аеродинамічне явище, що характеризується нестійкими автоколиваннями конструкцій, проектування тонкостінних конструкцій та моніторинг стану конструкцій. Також проаналізовано близько 30 рецензованих джерел, які дали змогу виділити основні напрямки для впровадження в проектування та аналіз ракетно-космічної галузі. Недоліком аналізу PGML можна вважати обмежену кількість опублікованих джерел, що може бути дещо поверхневим. Проаналізовано ключові реалізації PGML – зокрема PINNs, GAPINN, NSFnet, multi-fidelity та hybridmodels – і їх ефективність у випадках обмеженої вибірки. Увагу також приділено проблемам інтерпретованості моделей, зокрема застосуванню explainable ML, символічної регресії та баєсівських підходів для верифікації рішень у критичних сценаріях. Визначено основні виклики для широкого впровадження PGML: налаштування балансу між фізичними та статистичними компонентами, обмеження масштабованості в багатофазних середовищах, складність сертифікації результатів, нестабільність при розв'язанні обернених задач. У результаті дослідження обґрунтовано, що PGML перестає бути окремим напрямом застосування машинного навчання й постає як нова епістемологічна платформа для формування інженерних гіпотез.

Ключові слова: PGML, PINN, флатер, втомна міцність, моделювання з різнорівневою точністю, турбулентне замикання

Introduction. Machine learning is gradually transforming the approach to computational mechanics, making analytical modeling more flexible and interpretable. Instead of relying solely on approximate empirical methods, we can now create models grounded in physical laws. This is particularly crucial when data is incomplete, experiments are costly, and geometric conditions are constantly changing. These factors have led to the emergence of a new approach—Physics-Guided Machine Learning (PGML). It serves as a bridge between physical laws (e.g., conservation equations or symmetries) and the ability of deep neural networks to adapt to specific tasks. As a result, we can achieve accurate outcomes even with incomplete data [25].

PGML is not a single universal system but a collection of solutions. In these, physical principles are integrated into models either by modifying the loss function or by embedding symmetries into the neural network's structure. For example, in [19] explains how geometric constraints help models operate within feasible states. One example of PGML is Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs), which use partial differential equations and automatic differentiation to combine mathematics with real physical processes [12].

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications. PGML has been actively evolving as a practical technology in aerospace engineering. Recent studies demonstrate that PGML models increasingly handle incomplete or unstable data while maintaining consistency with physical laws [3,10, 18, 19, 25]. These models are

gradually moving away from simple experimental approximations and beginning to explain results through clear structural parameters.

In the aerospace field, PGML holds particular significance. Experiments are costly, and geometric and material conditions can change rapidly within a single project. PGML enables the integration of physical laws into the learning process, reducing the need for large datasets. This lowers model validation costs and aids in optimizing designs, even with limited computational resources [1,5]. Moreover, within explainable artificial intelligence, PGML not only predicts but also demonstrates how each parameter impacts the outcome, making model logic more transparent, as noted by authors [3,11, 28].

Aim and objectives. This work is dedicated to reviewing how PGML functions in aerospace mechanics tasks. We focused on four main areas: material fatigue prediction, flutter modeling, thin-walled shell analysis, and structural health monitoring. Particular attention was given to how physical principles—equations of motion, boundary conditions, or material properties—are integrated into the learning process. Additionally, challenges related to model scalability, validation, and the development of models capable of handling incomplete or conflicting data while remaining interpretable were examined.

Methodology. This study describes the application of PGML in applied tasks, with a focus on the aerospace industry. The analysis involved a review of research from 2019–2025, which confirmed the effectiveness of PGML in tasks related to mechanics, dynamics, and materials science.

Key Research Areas:

- Material Fatigue Prediction involves assessing damage accumulation in materials (e.g., metals or composites) used in aerospace structures under cyclic loading. Fatigue leads to the formation of microcracks, their growth, and ultimately the failure of components such as wings or fuselages.

- Flutter is an aerodynamic phenomenon characterized by unstable self-sustained oscillations of structures (e.g., wings or tail fins) due to the interaction of aerodynamic forces, elastic deformations, and inertial effects. Flutter modeling involves determining critical flight speeds at which instabilities occur and analyzing structural dynamics.

- Thin-Walled Shells (e.g., fuselage skins or fuel tanks) are key components of aerospace structures. Analysis includes evaluating stresses, deformations, stability (e.g., resistance to buckling under compression), and behavior under external loads (pressure, shear, bending).

- Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) involves continuous or periodic assessment of the integrity of aerospace components (e.g., wings, fuselage) using sensors to detect damage such as cracks, corrosion, or composite delamination.

Publications were primarily sourced from peer-reviewed journals: Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar.

Search Keywords: “PGML,” “PINNs,” “flutter,” “aerospace engineering”. In-

clusion Criterion: Application of PGML in any technical field. Exclusion Criterion: Publications lacking original research data.

Each publication was analyzed across two aspects: relevance, novelty, and timeliness; and applicability to the aerospace industry. This approach enables the evaluation of PGML's potential integration into rocket and space technology and identifies key application scenarios.

Limitations: PGML is a relatively new approach, and information, particularly in the context of aerospace, remains limited. Early publications with relevant data only began appearing in 2019. Some studies have not yet undergone verification or indexing and thus cannot be considered. Additionally, certain abstracts may not reflect physical accuracy. These limitations do not diminish the value of the presented research but cannot be entirely ignored.

Research Results. PGML paradigm emerges at the intersection of three fields: numerical modeling, hypothetical descriptions, and empirical dependencies. A key feature of these approaches is their structural reliance on known physical laws, such as conservation equations, boundary conditions, and functional constraints. [22] emphasizes that this structured approach allows models to remain physically consistent even with limited training data.

The formal implementation of PGML involves two primary trajectories for integrating physics. The first is modifying the loss function by adding penalty components to minimize violations of physical equations. The second is embedding physical symmetries or invariances into the model's architecture. This principle underpins the NSFnet architecture, which models Navier-Stokes equations in incompressible media while accounting for hydrodynamic flow structures [12].

One of the most developed PGML directions is Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs). Their methodology involves training not only on empirical or simulated data but also on residuals of physical equations. As a result, the model can address both forward problems, such as system dynamics modeling, and inverse problems related to parameter identification or reconstructing internal fields from external measurements [9, 24].

A distinctive feature of PINNs is their ability to handle latent variables. Even with incomplete parameter sets, the model compensates for uncertainty by incorporating physical regularities. This makes PINNs widely applicable in fields like shell mechanics, composite vibration analysis, and wave propagation modeling in aerodynamic environments, as confirmed by studies [18, 23].

Alongside PINNs, hybrid models combining classical numerical modeling with data-driven machine learning methods are actively advancing. For example, simulation results from the finite element method can serve as input data for a neural network that refines or corrects local errors [1]. This approach allows for accounting for inaccuracies in theoretical assumptions through feedback from empirical data.

Another promising direction within PGML is symbolic regression. This approach generates an explicit mathematical formula that reflects the relationship between input and output variables, bypassing the opaque structure of neural networks.

For instance, in a study on steel strength, symbolic regression enabled the combination of high prediction accuracy with a physical model [3].

A distinct class of PGML approaches focuses not on modifying the loss function but on restructuring the feature space. In such models, physical parameters—such as Young’s modulus, Reynolds number, or Poisson’s ratio—are used not only as input variables but also as the basis for creating informative features that guide the learning process. This strategy has been successfully applied in research on composite systems and nanostructures [13, 23]. It reduces the number of parameters, accelerates the learning process, and enhances result generalization in environments with high uncertainty.

In materials mechanics, PGML has gained particular traction in fatigue prediction tasks, which traditionally require extensive cyclic testing. This is especially challenging for additively manufactured parts or metamaterials, where the microstructure is irregular and difficult to describe. Mechanistic machine learning enables the integration of physical regularities, including topological dependencies, into the model-building process for predicting fatigue strength [1]. This approach accounts for inhomogeneities and local stress concentrations without requiring a detailed description of the microstructure.

PGML models are particularly effective in scenarios with limited data samples. For example, a PINN-based approach for fatigue life prediction simultaneously learns from sparse empirical observations and prior physical constraints [4]. This method avoids overfitting, common in classical machine learning models with scarce data, and ensures consistency with known fatigue failure laws.

PGML integrates physical laws with machine learning to model complex aerospace engineering problems, such as material fatigue and flutter prediction. Elasticsearch[15], with its vector search capabilities[16] complements PGML by storing and analyzing vector representations of physical data, like defect signals or aerodynamic states. Using models like PINNs, PGML generates embeddings that Elasticsearch indexes in vector fields, enabling fast similarity searches algorithms. This synergy enhances real-time structural monitoring and anomaly detection, though challenges like balancing physical-statistical components and scalability persist.

Another paradigm, based on symbolic regression, enabled the creation of an analytical formula for predicting the fatigue strength of steels, accounting for cycle counts and stress levels [3]. This approach not only achieves accuracy comparable to neural networks but also maintains interpretability, which is critical for verification in aviation engineering.

Particular attention should be given to the issue of multiaxial loading, characteristic of real-world aircraft operating conditions. Combining PINNs with materials mechanics enables modeling the service life of components subjected to complex cyclic loads across multiple planes [10]. This approach integrates the stress-strain state into the model structure and accounts for loading history—a key factor in failure.

Among the current directions of PGML, multi-fidelity architectures hold a prominent place. These enable the combination of simulations with varying levels of accuracy, compensating for each method’s limitations through integration into a uni-

fied predictive framework. For instance, combining low- and high-fidelity data is applied to predict the fatigue life of components produced via additive manufacturing [26]. This approach accounts for complex geometries and structural inhomogeneities, which render classical empirical models impractical.

In parallel, the importance of explainable machine learning (ML) models is growing. In a study by [28], a machine learning architecture was proposed for assessing the fatigue strength of steel produced through laser cladding. This model not only ensures high accuracy but also enables visualization of the contributions of individual factors, such as layer thickness, temperature, or defect type. This enhances trust in the results among materials science experts and supports auditing of the prediction logic, which is critical for regulatory compliance.

Thin-walled shell elements are widely used in aerospace structures due to efficiency requirements. However, mathematical modeling of such structures, especially those with anisotropic properties or variable thickness, remains a complex challenge. To address this, a PINN model in non-Euclidean geometry was developed, avoiding the rigidity of classical methods and demonstrating high accuracy without requiring discretization [2].

A similar approach is applied to multilayer laminated plates, where the neural network architecture accounts for stresses and deformations at layer interfaces [27]. This is particularly relevant for modeling aircraft skin. Some estimates suggest that PINN efficiency increases when input feature spaces incorporate symmetry, anisotropy, and layered geometry [13]. In cases with limited data samples, this strategy ensures the model's physical consistency.

In the dynamic analysis of composites, PGML's prospects are confirmed through practical applications. For example, a research team implemented a PINN to model a variable-thickness plate, typical of aviation panels with complex topologies [23]. This model provided accurate reconstruction of structural behavior without requiring mesh refinement, making it suitable for rapid optimization or adaptation to varying geometries.

Structurally oriented PGML models are increasingly addressing complex geometries and continuum processes previously modeled solely within classical mechanics. An example of such integration is a study that applied peridynamics formalism to model crack propagation in thin-walled structures [17]. The model accounted for nonlocal interactions, typically not captured by classical approaches, particularly in cases of localized damage and progressive failure.

In practical contexts, PGML models demonstrate generalization capabilities across variable geometric scenarios. For instance, the effectiveness of PINNs was evaluated in mechanics tasks for cellular and sandwich structures, highlighting the model's ability to generalize results across different parameters without losing physical consistency [6, 29].

In stability tasks, where physical nonlinearities and geometric instabilities complicate the accuracy of classical methods, PGML shows significant potential. Specifically, a model with physically grounded constraints was developed to predict the buckling of cylindrical shells under compression [14]. This approach reduced er-

ror by 20% compared to traditional numerical methods.

Flutter—a phenomenon of self-sustained oscillations arising from the interaction of aerodynamic, inertial, and elastic forces—poses a significant challenge for compressor and turbine engineering due to the complexity of prediction and high risk of failures. A hybrid PGML model, combining empirical data with analytical aerodynamic constraints, demonstrated accurate prediction of flutter boundaries without excessive computational load [21].

A distinct niche within PGML is occupied by models addressing turbulent flows. For example, constructing turbulent closure models in the context of wake mixing for low-pressure turbine blades requires integrating direct numerical simulation (DNS) data with physical constraints [7]. This approach enables modeling turbulent structures without fully solving the Navier-Stokes equations.

The integration of explainable machine learning into PGML models introduces a new level of transparency. Specifically, an approach for predicting turbulence coefficients during transonic flow was proposed, combining the accuracy of deep models with interpretable prediction logic [11]. Applying explainability principles allows tracing cause-and-effect relationships between flow properties and instability characteristics, which is particularly crucial for certification procedures.

The integration of PGML with tasks involving the solution of Navier-Stokes equations in complex geometries opens new possibilities for high-precision fluid dynamics simulations. For instance, the NSFnet PINN architecture models incompressible flows without relying on traditional mesh discretization [12]. This is critical for capturing local effects such as shading, flow separation, or vortex formation, which significantly impact the flutter characteristics of turbomachinery blades.

Another promising approach is implemented in the GAPINN (Geometry-Aware Physics-Informed Neural Network) architecture [18]. This architecture is tailored to the complex geometry of turbomachinery components, enabling flow modeling in high-curvature channels without the need for mesh redesign. This approach creates the foundation for real-time modeling of actual structures within the design cycle.

A separate niche within PGML involves models combining inverse problems with multi-fidelity architectures. Researchers [9] developed a PGML framework for inverse modeling in the context of solid mechanics. Although the study focuses on general mechanical scenarios, its principles remain relevant for tasks requiring the reconstruction of material or flow parameters from limited data, such as in flutter modeling.

A research group [5] adapted PGML for diagnosing the condition of aerospace structures based on wave propagation models. Combining Gaussian processes with physical equations not only improved defect detection accuracy with limited data but also enabled quantitative assessment of prediction uncertainty, which is critical for technical decision-making.

An example of applying PGML in structural health monitoring (SHM) scenarios is presented in a study [20]. It utilized a piezosensor network for damage localization in aluminum plates. The model combined machine learning algorithms with the

physical principles of wave propagation, demonstrating the ability to detect damage even with partial signal loss. This reduced reliance on template-based methods, which scale poorly for structures with variable geometry. Incorporating physical constraints into the training process not only enhances reliability but also ensures model robustness to variations [5].

With the increasing complexity of structures and demands for residual life prediction, PGML opens new opportunities for integrating diagnostic methods with computational modeling. Despite the initially empirical nature of the approach, studies lay the foundation for combining it with physically verified material fatigue models. This, in turn, enables the development of risk assessment tools grounded in structural logic and diagnostic data [26].

However, the widespread application of PGML in practice faces several methodological challenges. One of these is the tuning of the loss function, which requires balancing physical and statistical components. Overemphasizing physical constraints can impair the model's ability to capture real data, while insufficient consideration of them leads to a loss of physical meaning [27].

Another significant challenge is scalability. Most studies demonstrate PGML's effectiveness in localized tasks, but transitioning to full-scale models with multiphysics effects, such as aerothermo structural interactions, increases computational complexity. This issue is not always resolved even with modified PINN architectures [9,12]. Despite PGML's advantages over "black box" models, the complexity of its architecture remains a barrier to adoption in critical industries. Proposed solutions include symbolic regression and sensitivity analysis, which allow tracking the contribution of each parameter to predictions and increasing confidence in results [3,11].

A significant issue is solving inverse problems. In cases where internal material properties need to be inferred from surface data, models are sensitive to noise. This can be addressed through stabilization using regularizers or Bayesian methods [9, 18].

Practical validation of models remains an open question. Despite numerous successful simulations, implementing PGML in serial production requires formal procedures to ensure compliance with industry standards [1, 21].

The evolution of PGML is closely tied to advancements in related fields, such as digital twins, sensor networks, inverse modeling techniques, and turbulence closure. A general trend toward transitioning from classical analysis to hybrid simulation systems with embedded adaptive logic is evident in the works of several researchers [7,8].

Discussion. The advancement of PGML in predicting material fatigue strength is based not only on analytical assumptions but also on the models' ability to adapt to conditions of uncertainty. A review of applications in composites and additive systems shows that physics-guided learning enables the modeling of material behavior in scenarios where traditional approaches face methodological or computational limitations.

PINNs and PGML are not mutually exclusive concepts. On the contrary, they

form a unified methodological field, combining physical grounding, architectural adaptability, and learning flexibility. The choice of a specific approach depends on the volume of available data, the type of system, the nature of the equations, and computational speed requirements. In each case, the model results from a balance between empirical data and theoretical foundations.

The gradual expansion of PGML to tasks involving uncertainty, such as modeling with random parameters, requires integration with quantitative risk analysis methods. Thus, PGML emerges not only as a technical tool but also as a component of the intellectual context of modern engineering.

In the context of mechanics tasks, PGML's effectiveness is particularly evident in three scenarios: when data is limited, when a system is governed by known laws but numerical implementation is complex, and when modeling results must be interpretable, not merely accurate. These conditions are typical in industries where the cost of error is critical and experimental data is limited [4].

PGML is used for flutter analysis in compressor elements. A model combining aerodynamic equations with real-world data delivers accurate results without requiring complex numerical simulations [21]. A similar approach was applied to model turbulence in low-pressure turbines, where PGML helped create a model describing air mixing behind blades [7]. This demonstrates that PGML is increasingly combined with explainable machine learning, particularly when local aerodynamic effects are critical.

Unlike classical systems, PGML models for SHM allow retraining without losing physical consistency. They can adapt to new structures or conditions while maintaining alignment with fundamental mechanics laws. This makes the approach relevant not only for designing new systems but also for upgrading existing control infrastructures.

In aviation structure monitoring, PGML also shows excellent results. By combining sensor data with physical models of wave propagation, these models accurately identify damage locations, accounting for the object's geometry and signal characteristics [5]. A similar approach was used in piezosensor systems, where PGML adapted diagnostics to scenarios involving signal loss or structural changes [20]. In these cases, the model becomes not just a computational tool but part of a system that supports engineers in decision-making.

Conclusions. This work reviewed existing publications on Physics-Guided Machine Learning and analyzed how these studies can be applied in the aerospace industry. Specific areas where PGML is already utilized were examined, namely: material fatigue prediction, flutter modeling, thin-walled shell analysis, and structural health monitoring.

Thus, it can be confidently stated that PGML is not merely a set of algorithms but a new way of thinking in science and engineering. Instead of building models "bottom-up" — from data to results — PGML operates in the opposite direction: it starts with physical laws and transforms them into computational models. This approach is not about randomly selecting network architectures but about letting the

problem's logic dictate how the model learns. Each physical principle becomes an integral part of the algorithm [22]. In aerospace engineering, PGML transforms the approach to machine learning: data is no longer the sole source of information. Instead, knowledge of physical laws, equations, symmetries, or boundary conditions is directly embedded into the model, guiding its learning process and narrowing the range of possible solutions [12].

These examples underscore a key point: the success of PGML requires not only knowledge of algorithms but also a deep understanding of the physical principles underlying the problem. PGML does not replace theory—it extends it. It is not just a new type of neural network but a novel approach to engineering challenges, combining theory, data, and computation. By embedding physical laws into the learning process, PGML enhances model interpretability and ensures consistency with real-world behavior. This integration leads to more robust and generalizable solutions, particularly in domains where data alone is insufficient.

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